

METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING ELEMENTARY SCHOOL PUPILS TO WRITE BEAUTIFULLY

Murodkosimova Dilfuza Turgunmirza kizi

Master's degree at Jizzakh State Pedagogical University "Theory and methodology of Education and training (Primary Education)"

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Abstract. *This article describes the physiological basis for the formation of beautiful writing skills in primary school students and the methods of beautiful writing. Teaching students to write beautifully depends on the qualifications, experience of each teacher. Highlights information about elementary school teachers writing skills, techniques for teaching beautiful writing, and principles for teaching beautiful writing to students.*

Keywords: *abstract, principle of awareness, genetic principle, principle of repetition, principle of exhibitionism.*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching elementary students beautiful writing is the foundation of literacy. In addition to fluency in oral and written speech of students and training them as mature people in every way, from teaching in the primary class, it is also intended to bring them to adulthood as those who strive for beauty, who strive to create beauty that can feel it from the heart.

The physiological basis for the formation of beautiful writing skills in the development of Primary School students as a harmonious personality is of particular importance.

Teaching students to write beautifully also depends on the qualifications, experience of each teacher. In this, attention, memory, perception are among the main motivating factors for a child to write beautifully.

Attention is a process in which all the thoughts and attention of a person are focused on one goal. Elementary students are more likely to attract their attention to the correct expression of the shapes of the letters in the writing process. Words and sentences spoken cannot be perceived without knowing the correct writing forms of letters, without understanding the correct writing forms. That is, when writing each letter, memory is first of all important for attention, perception of the correct writing of its elements and the fact that they remember these letters.

The model writing of the teacher is the main factor in the formation of the correct writing in children. Teaching to write is often achieved through imitation. A teacher's writing on a classroom board or student's notebook during their freshman year is seen as an original because students copy it from it into their notebook. Therefore, the teacher's writing must be correct and beautiful.

In order for a clear and fluent writing to be formed in the student, the teacher must focus all the attention of the student on the graphic shape of the letter, so that it does not merge with another letter. Students are required to develop correct writing skills with beautiful writing, to systematically carry out the work of teaching beautiful writing. This involves the gradual reproduction and complication of writing materials. To do this, too, it will be necessary for students to carry out continuous control examination work, not limited to the Daily skill of the correct writing. It is better for students to know the control time in advance, because before that they will take the time to prepare the deficit in the pen and the notebook. After writing, children exchange

their work with their comrades and analyze it together with the teacher. The best works are attached to the reader's corner. During the control, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that it is written in compliance with the rules of beautiful writing, the letters are written correctly, the text is easily read, the writing is uniform, the text is for reading, and the planning of saving paper.

It is necessary to regularly check not only the written work of the mother tongue in the lessons, but also the student's writing in other educational subjects. In order for the control - examination work to be comparable to each other, the study work is attached to a special place. To do this, it is necessary to write control - examination work on a separate piece of paper, and it should be based on a not very large text. In order to compare the improvement of writing skills, it is necessary to maintain the control - examination work of each student.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Beautiful writing and the methodology of its teaching are pedagogical science. A person can communicate his opinion to other people in oral and written form. There are similarities and differences in this form of speech, which in their place have advantages. Oral speech is spoken out of sound and is intended for hearing. It serves as a means of communication in the time of the speech process of people. Written speech, on the other hand, is written through permanent signs that are perceived on the basis of vision, such as stone, wood, leather, metal, paper. Writing is the powerful means by which people exchange ideas and acquire knowledge. Written speech connects generations, is kept long. Thanks to writing, a person is thought, the knowledge acquired by mankind reaches from generation to generation, lives forever. Method of writing according to the sample. One of the most basic ways to teach beautiful writing is to sample and write The Shape of the letters. Each letter sample should be displayed on the board with the attention of all readers, or separately in a notebook to some readers.

Copy method. This method can be applied to readers who cannot correctly imagine The Shape of the letter, fall or leave the notebook lines when writing. For example, when a student makes a mistake in writing a capital letter A, the teacher displays them in pencil in a notebook, represented by dots, while the student walks over it in ink. This method broadly shapes the reader's perception of this knowledge. Along with the positive aspects of this method, there are also negative aspects. Only such exercises will help to grow arm movement. For a long time, children who write in such a way have difficulty writing The Shape of the letters independently or according to the pattern. Method of writing by imagination. In addition to the above methods, children are trained by typing the shape of the letters in the air through imagination. The teacher allows the letters or links that he or she indicates to the board, how to write to the students, how the pen moves in the air, to be written in a notebook after the students have formed an idea. Such exercises cultivate the interests of students and also allow them to perform physical exercises.

DISCUSSION

The discipline of teaching beautiful writing is also growing and developing, having its own historical sources, among other disciplines. Below we will reflect on the most basic writing methods that elementary school teachers need to know. These methods and methods are as follows:

1. Linear method.
2. Genetic method.
3. Method of writing according to the sample.
4. Copy method.
5. Method of writing by imagination.

6. Rhythmic method (number-tone).
7. Method of analyzing letter forms.
8. Method of conscious mastery of writing skills.
9. Hand movement exercise method.

The principle of teaching beautiful writing

1. The principle of awareness.
2. Genetic principle.
3. The principle of repetition.
4. The principle of exhibitionism.
5. The principle of taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the child.
6. The principle of teaching writing at the same time as teaching reading.
7. The principle of the connection of beautiful writing with spelling.
8. The principle of the connection of literate writing with graphic knowledge.

RESULTS

1. The principle of awareness. When teaching beautiful writing, it is important to strictly adhere to this principle when improving the skills of the student's Hussite. According to this principle, the reader should know how and in what order to write The Shape of the letter, be able to correctly outline the slope, height and width of the letter. When connecting letters to letters, it is assumed to achieve handlessness. When holding a pen, it is kept in mind that the distance between the tip of the pen and the finger is 1.5-2 cm.

2. Genetic principle. the genetic principle plays a big role in the formation of beautiful writing skills. The reader is taught to write easy, simple letters in shape first, based on this principle. As you know, some letters have a soda look, and there is no difficulty in writing them. Therefore, when teaching beautiful writing, initial and lowercase letters are first grouped, and on the basis of this grouping, the shape is gradually shifted from easy letters to more complex, the writing to slightly more complex ones. For example, lowercase Group 1 includes I, n, m, R, etc. Since these letters consist of loop forms, there will be no difficulty in writing. Also, on the basis of the genetic principle, writing exercises are performed in the order of letter, syllable, word, sentence, text, from easy to complex.

3. The principle of repetition. In order not to forget about beautiful writing exercises, it is very important to repeat systematically. The principle of repetition is the basis of automation of the writing process. In beautiful writing, following hygienic rules will give a good result to remind. Work such as following the writing slope, writing letters without hands, correctly summing up the distance between letters, words and repeating the following the rules regarding writing, analyzing the writing, comparing them is carried out on the principle of repetition. It is followed that it is carried out in the manner of correcting mistakes, that it does not turn into an ineffective exercise.

4. The principle of exhibitionism. Visual aids are also of great importance in teaching beautiful writing. Visual media include "sit right!" includes posters, cartons with the expression of printed letter forms, calligraphy, and typesetting from the hands of readers. When teaching to form a written form of a letter, its printed form is indicated and different aspects are explained. Well-chosen and skillfully used visual aids improve the quality and effectiveness of the lesson.

5. The principle of taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the child. Taking into account the individual characteristics of the student begins with the transfer to the previous parts, taking into account his height. When the part is suitable for the reader, he does not

have difficulty writing, does not get tired quickly, writes beautifully. Taking into account the individual nature of the student. It is also intended to transfer visually impaired pupils to the side of a light falling window, and a child with hearing organ defects to the front partitions. It is known that pupils who incorrectly hold the pen between the fingers are also found, due to which special attention is also paid to the child's grip on the pen. Writing letters in a notebook with a slope of 65° degrees plays the main roll.

6. The principle of teaching writing at the same time as teaching reading. The requirements of the program imply that teaching writing is done at the same time as teaching reading. At the initial stage of teaching, reading and writing are tied up. This method is K.D.Ushinsky was applied from the side, which is still used in the era. Writing is also taught at a time when the reader possesses good reading qualities (correct, conscious, fast and expressive reading). Negative writing and reading provide for the child's speech development (vocabulary wealth, speech-making skills, logical connection of speech). A poorly educated child will find it difficult to master the script, because after a choking reading qualification, a booming writing qualification will be formed.

7. The principle of the connection of literate writing with graphic knowledge. Beautiful writing is closely related to spelling. Taking care of the spelling erudition of the reader means the accuracy of the language, the correct expression of thought, the care to deal with people without mutual error. Therefore, during the period of knowledge training, the basis is laid for the formation of spelling skills in children, along with the formation of graphic skills.

8. During the period of teaching, the student learns in a practical way how to write a sentence with a capital letter, move the part of the word that does not fit the line to the next line, the name of the people, the use of a capital letter in the names placed on the animals. Writing words, sentences, texts in beautiful writing lessons, checking their spelling gradually forms orthographic elegance, laying the groundwork for their careful mastery of spelling rules. A person's written speech is formed through letters.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that in beautiful writing lessons, the formation of literate writing with graphic skills is the main task. The exact spelling of each letter ensures that the writing is clear and fluent. To do this, it is important to correctly write The Shape of the letters, to connect them correctly. We can say that writing evenly without pressing letters, connecting elements without separating them, correctly placing words in a row, marking writing time, the implementation of analytical work (syllable-sound, sound-letter, spelling analysis), that is, phonetic-graphic analysis, are important dates.

REFERENCES

1. Gülomov M. " Teaching elementary students to husnykhat "Tashkent" teacher " 1970. Gülomov M.
2. "Hansycha methodology" Tashkent "teacher" 1976
3. Gülomov M. " Formation of beautiful writing " Tashkent 2002.
4. Elementary education improved curriculum, mother tongue, "Elementary Education" No. 6, 2005.
5. Abdullayev.Y "methodology of teaching correspondence in the old school "Tashkent" teacher " 1996 year.

6. Abdullayev.Y "companion" educational manual Tashkent "teacher" 1996.
7. Abdullayev.Y, Yo'ldoshev.Sh " new alphabet and spelling "Tashkent" teacher " 2000.
8. Abdullayev. Q, Nazarov.Q, Yo'ldoshev.Sh "teaching Salvation" Tashkent "teacher" 1996.